

New observations on the occurrence of *Aristotelia calastomella* (Christoph, 1872) in Hungary (Lepidoptera, Gelechiidae)

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Abstract. The author presents new bionomic and geographical data on *Aristotelia calastomella* (Christoph, 1872). He concludes that the species reaches the western limit of its geographical distribution in the Pannonian biogeographical region. Forest-steppe remnants in the Danube-Tisza Interfluvium region of Hungary are relics of degraded, ancient habitats of the species. The fragmented occurrence of *Aristotelia calastomella* in Hungary undoubtedly justifies a genetic comparison of the Russian and Hungarian populations.

Keywords. Bionomics, geographical spread, fragmentation.

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Résumé. L'auteur présente de nouvelles données bionomiques et géographiques sur *Aristotelia calastomella* (Christoph, 1872). Il conclut que l'espèce atteint la limite occidentale de sa répartition géographique dans la région biogéographique pannonienne. Les vestiges de forêt-steppe dans la région de l'interfluvium Danube-Tisza en Hongrie sont des reliques d'anciens habitats dégradés de l'espèce. Selon lui, la présence fragmentée d'*Aristotelia calastomella* en Hongrie justifierait une comparaison génétique des populations russes et hongroises.

Introduction

In this journal (Fazekas 2024, pp. 29–34) I discussed in detail the bionomics and geographical distribution of *Aristotelia calastomella*. After the online publication of that paper, Ferenc Buschmann (H-Jászberény) informed me that he has additional specimens in his collection. He collected these specimens in previously unknown localities. The new habitats are different from those previously known so their description and presentation here are important for the general improvement of knowledge concerning species and will help the research into the species and facilitate the discovery of new habitats. I have studied and used the following sources to prepare this thesis: Bölöni, Molnár & Kun 2011; Fazekas 2024; Kocsis & Schweitzer 2009; Molnár & Kun 2000; Molnár 2008; Molnár & Borhidi 2003.

Results

New data. 3 ex Alattyán, Bereki-erdő, 8.VIII.2015; 30.VII.2016; 8 ex Farnos, sziki tanösvény, 4–9.VIII.2017; 3 ex, Farnos, sziki tanösvény, 01.VI.2018. leg. et in coll. Buschmann (private collection, H-Jászberény). All specimens were recovered from a battery-powered UV light tube so-called bucket trap. 125-watt mercury vapour lamp did not attract the image.

Habitats. The vegetation of the two new sites (Alattyán and Farnos) differs significantly (Buschmann pers. comm.). The soil of the Farnos site is sandy, strongly saline, dominated by *Camphorosma annua* and *Festuca pseudovine*, lacking *Peucedanum* species and *Aster sedifolius*. The latter species is replaced by *Aster tripolium*. The larvae may live either on *Aster tripolium* or on *Camphorosma annua* plants, but it may also be possible that they prefer both species.

Fig. 1. Study sites with occurrences of *Aristotelia calastomella* in Hungary. Explanation: the arrow shows the new sites, number 1 is the first observation, number 2 is the second observation (after Fazekas 2024, modified)

Fig. 2. The geographical distribution of the tall herb salt meadow steppes in Hungary (after Bölöni et al. 2011, modified). The large stands in Hungary are now mostly protected in National Parks, local protected areas and Natura 2000-sites (after Bölöni et al. 2011, modified).

Fig 3. Approximate distribution ranges of forest-steppes in Trans-Palaearctic. In Europe, it reaches its western limit in the Pannonian Biogeographical Region (black circle). Hypothetically, additional *Aristotelia calastomella* meta-populations should be sought in this vegetation zone, especially in southern Siberia. (Map by Erdős et al. 2022, modified)
The salt meadow steppe is not marked.

General description of Alattyán (Bereki-erdő = Bereki forest): the new site belongs to the Hungarian Lowland (Eupannonicum) and is in the north-western part of the Tiszántúl flora (Crisicum). The typical plant community is the tall herb salt meadow steppes (Peucedano-Asteretum sedifolii Soó 1947 corr. Borhidi 1996), an important member of the forest-steppe complex. The endemic habitat of the Hungarian Great Plain, although similar in composition but with a significantly different species composition, grasslands and tall fescue are not uncommon in continental Eurasia. It is related to the cool-continental plant communities of southern Siberia and is on the list of highly protected plant communities in Hungary. This area was a vast marshland before the Zagyva River was regulated. Military maps from 1885 and surveys from 1929 demonstrate this. The climate of the area can be described as follows: The mean temperature in January is -2 degrees Celsius, and the mean temperature in July is +20,5 degrees Celsius. The average annual temperature is 10–11 degrees Celsius. The annual water deficit is close to 300 mm. Only fragments of ancient woody vegetation remain.

Habitat of Farnos (sziki tanösvény): Anyone who wants to see a real salt steppe area in Hungary will find it here, near the village of Farnos. In Hungary, there are very few species of moths that are restricted to saline habitats, such as: *Narraga tessularia* (Metzner, 1845), *Hadula dianthi hungarica* (F. Wagner, 1930), *Saragossa porosa kenderesiensis* (Kovács, 1968), *Gortyna borelii lunata* (Freyer, 1838). In Hungary, only here, in the meadows of the Tápió region, the two main saline soil types, the so-called “solonchalk”, where salt is extracted on the surface, and the “solonyec”, where it is extracted below the soil, can be found side by side.

Summary

This paper summarizes the distribution of *Aristotelia calastomella* in Hungary using new bionomic data. It concludes that the species is highly fragmented and that the newer localities are located at the westernmost limits of its geographic distribution. It suggests a comparative genetic study of the Russian and Hungarian populations.

Acknowledgements

Thanks to Ferenc Buschmann (H-Jászberény) for information about the specimens collected and the characteristics of the habitats. I thank Péter Gergely (H-Csobánka) for his useful comments on the manuscript. For the final linguistic proofreading, I thank Colin W. Plant (UK-Bishops Stortford).

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